

This repository contains the data and code used in the following study:

Rahmani, J., Shen, C., & Ameli, A. A. (2026). Regionalization of hydrologic behavior and pothole water storage dynamics in the Prairie Pothole Region. *Water Resources Research*, 62(2), e2025WR040280.

For questions regarding this code release, please contact: jrahmani@eoas.ubc.ca.

Follow the below instructions to run the code:

1. Set up the environment

Use the provided `environment.yml` file in the main directory (`dHBV-Pot`) to create the conda environment.

- First: Install conda (if not already installed)
- Second: Run the following command to create the environment
`conda env create -f environment.yml`
- Third: run the following command to activate the environment
`conda activate dHBVPot_env`

2. Input data

An example dataset is provided in:

`./dHBV-Pot/PPR_example/01_Input_data`

This directory includes:

- Five .txt files
- A folder containing streamflow data (Excel format).

All datasets are preprocessed and ready to use.

3. Running the Code

The code in this repository relies on **relative paths** for accessing input data and modules. Therefore, all scripts must be executed from `./dHBV-Pot/PPR_example/02_Run`. Running the code from other directories may result in file not found errors or import issues.

- **train_dHBV_Pot.py**: Interface for training the regional dHBV-Pot model parameters
- **test_dHBV_Pot.py**: Interface for testing the trained regional dHBV-Pot model

Notes

- The code was originally developed on the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (Compute Canada) platform.
- The provided environment file has been simplified for portability.
- Minor differences may occur depending on system configuration.